

Poems: Say No to Drugs,She exists ,East or West Moms are the best

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SAY NO TO DRUGS

The power of addiction is for real,
And it's effects you really can't veil.

You think you'll try it once and it will let you go,
but trust me if you'll try it twice it will take away your soul.

You think it strengthens your mental health,
but my dear friend it takes away your ability to survive in this entire world.

SHE EXISTS

Till when will you doubt on me,
Till when will you damper my faith.
Till when will you question my integrity.

I am a woman of today,
I know how to build confidence ,
how to keep my faith, how to maintain my honour.

Here is a woman of today,
raise us, be with us, know us,
I am sure you'll never regret one day.

EAST OR WEST MOMS ARE THE BEST

East or West Moms are the best,
they are a nurse, a teacher, a supervisor at their best,
that's why I say these Moms are the best.

I can't imagine how they do all things,
to have her in life is really a bliss.

A mother always smells like a sweet rose,
She's humble , She's sweet, a mother's heart is made up of pure gold.